

SDN-enabled resource management for converged Fi-Wi 5G Fronthaul

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Abstract—Future mobile networks will offer high data rates based on high-capacity fronthaul. Current fronthaul design has two main components that communicate via the common public radio interface and fiber links, i.e., remote units (RUs) that implement simple signal processing and centralized baseband units (CBBUs) in high power-consuming data centers that perform complex network functions. Various functional splits between CBBUs and RUs are feasible, inducing trade-offs between centralization gains and bandwidth demands. This design lacks in capacity and flexibility, motivating the use of converged fiber-wireless (Fi-Wi) fronthaul with high-bandwidth fiber and millimeter-wave links, and splits that move functionalities to RUs reducing the delay demands. Further flexibility is offered by analog radio-over-fiber fronthaul that supports dynamic functional splitting via software-defined networking (SDN). Ensuring acceptable delay for all RUs, i.e., minimizing fronthaul grade-of-service (GoS), requires selection of CBBUs, channel bandwidth and functional splits of RUs. The split type affects fronthaul power consumption determining which fronthaul components are active and their processing power. Using a simulated annealing-based dynamic fronthaul resource allocation (DFRA) scheme, we jointly optimize GoS and power consumption in a novel SDN Fi-Wi fronthaul. Our results show that DFRA minimizes GoS and power consumption for all load levels outperforming baseline approaches.

Index Terms—Fronthaul, Fi-Wi, Functional split, SDN, 5G.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the fifth generation (5G) connections will be 13 times faster than current mobile connections and the generated traffic will increase three-fold comparing to a long term evolution advanced (LTE-A) connections by 2023, mobile network operators (MNOs) invest on fronthaul networks with multi-Gb/s capacity that can support future radio access networks (RANs) [1]. For 5G fronthaul, the cloud RAN (C-RAN) appears to be a promising solution. It places the network intelligence and radio signal processing to the centralized baseband units (CBBUs) in data centers (DCs) located separately from the remote units (RUs), which simply decode and reconstruct the digital signals and are close to end users [2]. C-RAN can be based on passive optical networks (PONs), where an optical line terminal connects CBBUs and RUs via optical fibers and passive power splitters. The low operational cost of PONs has motivated the development of various PON variants, e.g., time-division multiplexed PON (TDM-PON) that allocates different

time slots to RUs sharing the same optical wavelength and wavelength-division multiplexing PON (WDM-PON), where each RU uses its own dedicated wavelength. Furthermore, C-RANs that currently support LTE-A mobile networks employ digitized fronthaul schemes, e.g., common public radio interface (CPRI) and its 5G oriented enhanced version (eCPRI) that enables flexible radio data transmission via packet based fronthaul, e.g., Ethernet (ETH), over fiber links [3].

The digital CPRI based fronthaul has quite strict bandwidth and delay requirements as it directly transports complex, digitally sampled radio waveforms between CBBUs and RUs. The amount of functions that are performed in high energy consuming centralized DCs tends to inflate the capacity demands of the 5G fronthaul that is destined to support very high user data rates provided by RUs [4]. To address this issue, alternative fronthaul designs have been proposed that exploit the high bandwidth availability of fiber-optics and wireless connectivity in millimeter-wave (mmWave) frequency bands [5]. A promising converged fiber wireless (Fi-Wi) fronthaul design is the analog radio-over-fiber (RoF) fronthaul that enables an analog radio frequency or intermediate frequency signal to be transported over fiber and wireless fronthaul links [6].

As an additional means to overcome the fronthaul limitations for 5G new radio (5G NR), the 3rd generation partnership project (3GPP) has advocated for a less centralized fronthaul design where only some of the functions of LTE-A protocol layers are performed by CBBUs. Moving part of functions to RUs, i.e., the decrease of centralization degree using less centralized (higher layer) functional splits, induces less strict fronthaul delay requirements [7]. This functional splitting can be flexible via the adaptation of functions' location according to load levels using network virtualization [8]. The decision about the functional split type also affects the fronthaul power consumption, which varies according to the processing power required at CBBUs and RUs and the allocated bandwidth in fronthaul links [9]. In particular, the selection of fronthaul components that are active and the functions that they implement in order to guarantee acceptable fronthaul delay levels for all RUs, i.e., minimize the fronthaul grade-of-service (GoS), becomes a multi-faceted performance issue. It requires the timely resource allocation according to network load variations

that can be supported by the software defined networking (SDN) framework [10]. Virtualization facilitates the Fi-Wi fronthaul orchestration particularly for analog RoF fronthaul architectures that can use different functional splits and encompass various resources, e.g., CBBUs, optical wavelengths and wireless spectrum [11].

So far, the joint fronthaul GoS and power consumption optimization issue has not been extensively studied considering the functional splitting capability of fronthaul. Although there exist studies that address joint fronthaul resource allocation and power consumption optimization problems, they use fixed functional splitting and perform resource allocation considering the delay requirements of the different splits as constraints. For instance, the work in [12] presents a method that minimizes the joint cost of transmission delay and network component placement in edge computing enabled C-RAN, considering the latency limit thresholds under different functional split options and constraints related to bandwidth capacity, transmission distance and optical network power budget. In [13], the joint allocation to RUs of resource blocks in wireless domain and wavelengths in optical domain with the aim of minimizing the used fronthaul bandwidth and the number of occupied RUs is proposed.

In more recent works on fronthaul resource management, the idea of functional split adaptation has been explored. Customized split types for hybrid edge and C-RAN design have been studied for joint system power consumption and midhaul bandwidth usage optimization [14]. A C-RAN power consumption minimization problem is solved by determining the RU operation mode, the functional split type, the precoding design and the fronthaul signal compression resolution [15]. Only two PHY and MAC split types, which differentiate in whether precoding coefficients are estimated in CBBUs or RUs, are considered. Both of the aforementioned approaches evaluate architecture-specific functional splitting types that are different from those proposed by 3GPP. Aiming to assess the fronthaul performance using various functional splits, a joint fronthaul bandwidth and power allocation problem is solved for different functional split cases, resulting in the selection of a split type for all RUs supported by wireless fronthaul links [16]. Similarly, different functional split options are studied in [17], where the network energy consumption and the number of user handovers are jointly minimized by matching RUs with CBBUs. The work in [18] focuses on optical fronthaul with hierarchical edge and cloud network slices and functional splitting capabilities. The bandwidth in fronthaul links is allocated according to QoS requirements of slices but without optimizing power consumption.

For the dynamic selection of functional split type, network virtualization and SDN have been employed. In [19], the functional splits are decided according to an SDN-based scheme that maximizes the centralization degree under fronthaul bandwidth constraints are proposed. In [20], functional splitting is performed with the aim of maximizing the user data rate and minimizing the C-RAN deployment cost in terms of fronthaul bandwidth and computational resource utilization. Despite the fact that some of the existing methods support flexibility in functional splitting, they aim at selecting the most

centralized functional split type in order to improve the experienced data rates, without considering the fronthaul power consumption. Furthermore, they do not take into account the various resources used in Fi-Wi fronthaul architectures with SDN capabilities that seem to gain momentum as fronthaul solution.

Most works related to fronthaul resource allocation optimization with concurrent consideration of power consumption are not directly applicable to analog RoF fronthaul that exploits virtualization in order to adapt functional splitting and operation status of the CBBUs and the RUs (Table I). Acknowledging this gap in the literature, we formulate the joint GoS and power consumption problem in SDN-based Fi-Wi fronthaul in order to study the trade-offs of the concurrent minimization of these metrics. Considering the high computational complexity of an exhaustive search based solution, we employ simulated annealing (SA) in order to design a new heuristic fronthaul resource management algorithm that yields acceptable solutions in a timely manner [21]. We therefore present our solution that exploits virtualization to dynamically assign RUs to CBBUs, switching off CBBUs and DCs when needed, and configuring the functional splits between CBBUs and RUs. The contribution of our work can be summarized as follows:

- (i) *Description of SDN-enabled converged Fi-Wi fronthaul architecture that supports dynamic functional splitting:* We propose a new analog RoF fronthaul architecture that can support high capacity 5G NR RAN. With the aid of SDN framework, the fronthaul can be dynamically orchestrated considering two aspects: i) the resource management aspect that involves the allocation of CBBUs and RoF channel bandwidth to RUs and ii) the functional splitting aspect that refers to the decision regarding the functional split type that should be used between each RU and the CBBU that serves it.
- (ii) *Design of dynamic fronthaul resource allocation (DFRA) algorithm:* We formulate the joint GoS and power consumption minimization problem taking into account the particularities of the proposed analog RoF fronthaul with virtualization and dynamic functional splitting capabilities. Next, we propose a novel SDN based algorithm that relies on the SA logic in order to jointly optimize the two fronthaul performance metrics. The proposed algorithm is able to adjust the functional splitting according to the fronthaul load levels and jointly allocate CBBUs and RoF channel bandwidth to the RUs, guaranteeing that the delay constraints of each split type are met with the lowest possible fronthaul power consumption.
- (iii) *Extensive performance evaluation of DFRA algorithm under the influence of different RUs' load levels:* We assess the performance of the proposed algorithm in terms of GoS, power consumption, energy efficiency and centralization degree through extensive simulations. More specifically, we investigate scenarios with various fronthaul load levels induced by the use of different number of active RUs, 5G NR channel bandwidth of RUs and functional split types between CBBUs and RUs.

TABLE I: Overview of fronthaul resource management approaches

Approach	Dynamic functional split	SDN-based	Fronthaul design	Power consumption
Wang et al. [12]	×	×	C-RAN TDM-PON	×
Zhang et al. [13]	×	×	TWDM-PON	×
Alabbasi et al. [14]	Customized splits	×	Edge and centralized cloud	✓
Zhou et al. [15]	PHY and MAC splits	×	C-RAN	✓
Tohidi et al. [16]	Evaluation only	×	C-RAN	✓
Gupta et al. [17]	Evaluation only	×	C-RAN	✓
Song et al. [18]	✓	×	Edge cloud-based optical	×
Marotta et al. [19]	✓	✓	TWDM-PON	×
Matoussi et al. [20]	✓	✓	C-RAN	×
Proposed approach	✓	✓	Converged Fi-Wi	✓

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. The system model is described in Section II and, in Section III, the considered problem is formulated. The DFRA algorithm is presented in Section IV, whereas the performance evaluation is discussed in Section V. Finally, in Section VI, conclusions are drawn.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In this section, we describe the considered system model, the technical details of the network configuration and the basic notation we follow in the rest of the paper.

A. Fronthaul architecture and operation

We consider a network with an SDN based Fi-Wi fronthaul that is coordinated by the network manager (NM) and is based on a set of \mathcal{N} DCs, as in Fig. 1. The DCs may be part of the infrastructure of different MNOs and support several CBBUs and the corresponding remote radio heads (RRHs) that can communicate with the CBBUs via fiber links. The RRHs are connected via fiber links with the analog central office (ACO), which acts as a centralized analog BBU and is connected via ETH ports with the CBBUs. The ACO is able to receive the digital eCPRI signals that are generated by the CBBUs, extract their payload and load it to analog carriers that will be transported via the Fi-Wi fronthaul. We denote as $\mathcal{M} = \bigcup_{n=1}^{|\mathcal{N}|} \mathcal{M}_n$ the set of available CBBUs, where \mathcal{M}_n is the set of CBBUs operated by DC n . We assume that each CBBU manages the operation of one RRH and that a number of $|\mathcal{M}|$ RRHs are available.

A set of \mathcal{K} RUs communicate with the NM via SDN controllers and can connect via wireless links with the RRHs. The set of RUs that can be assigned to a CBBU and the corresponding RRH m that belong to DC n is denoted as $\mathcal{K}_{n,m}, n \in \mathcal{N}, m \in \mathcal{M}$, thus it holds that $\mathcal{K} = \bigcup \mathcal{K}_{n,m}$. Each RU can receive and decode signals from the ACO that are related to the downlink (DL) traffic of the users it serves, whereas it can encode analog signals for the uplink (UL) direction. The communication between CBBUs and RUs is performed via RoF channels that are described in Section II-B. Furthermore, each RU k serves the end users via 5G NR channels that use a total bandwidth b_k^{RU} in DL direction.

1) *SDN-based fronthaul control operation*: In the considered SDN-controllable converged Fi-Wi fronthaul, the high level structure of SDN that enables the abstraction of the physical infrastructure from the applications is used and three

types of layers are considered, i.e., the infrastructure layer, the controller layer and the application layer. The NM manages the ACO, the RRHs, the RUs and the ETH switches that reside in the infrastructure layer. The controller functionalities related to the network devices are located in the controller layer managed by the NM. Moreover, the NM can communicate with the devices via a southbound interface (SBI), e.g., OpenFlow, and is able to interact with the application layer managed by the MNO via a northbound interface (NBI).

All the fronthaul network devices are able to communicate with the NM via the corresponding control channels. More specifically, the ACO can create and transmit signals of the fronthaul control plane. Furthermore, each RU contains a mmWave antenna that can transmit control signals to the ACO via the RRH, using different frequency bands from those that support the data plane traffic, as it will be described in Section II-B.

For the fronthaul resource management, the NM employs SDN in order to obtain an overall view of the fronthaul and monitors its status, aggregating via the traffic monitor (TM) module the information regarding the network load in the ACO, the RRHs and the RUs, along with the channel conditions in the RRH-RU links. The information of TM module is used by the resource allocation module (RA) that optimizes the allocation of fronthaul resources in a centralized manner taking into account the network status and the performance requirements decided by the MNO. Once the RA module decides about the resources and the functional split types that should be used and notifies the network components about the new configuration.

2) *Functional splitting in considered architecture*: In the considered fronthaul design, functional splits between two different sets of components are employed (Fig. 2). Between the ACO and each RRH, the functional split is performed inside the physical layer, i.e., intra-PHY split (Option 7) [6]. A similar functional split is performed between each CBBU and the RUs as a default option in our architecture. However, the NM may choose a higher layer split in order to reduce the generated fronthaul load, e.g., MAC-PHY split (Option 6) or PDCP-RLC split (Option 2) [4].

The CBBUs and the RUs coordinate the radio access, implementing the 5G NR mobile protocol and form the eCPRI packets that carry the payload related to the selected functional split type. In the DL scenario that we study, the ACO combines the packets related to the set of RUs served by each CBBU and RRH into an ETH packet that is transmitted to the RUs

Fig. 1: SDN based Fi-Wi fronthaul

Fig. 2: Functional splits in converged Fi-Wi fronthaul

via the RRH. Each RU receives the packets emitted by the corresponding RRH and performs ETH packet processing in order to extract the payload related to the end users it serves.

As the functional split between CBBUs and RUs may vary, the NM is able to select the proper split type among a set of available options. Let us now define as $\mathcal{S} = \{s^{\min}, \dots, s^{\max}\}$ the set of available splits between CBBUs and RRHs, where s^{\min} and s^{\max} are the least centralized and most centralized split options, respectively. The RUs use functional splits denoted as $\mathbf{s} = (s_1, \dots, s_{|\mathcal{K}|})$, where $s_k \in \mathcal{S}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$ is the split used by RU k . In particular, for each RU k associated with CBBU m , packets are added to the queue of m with arrival rate λ_k (packets/sec). The type of the functional split used by the RUs and the number of users concurrently connected to each RU are two factors that affect the packet arrival rates, i.e., the fronthaul load at each CBBU.

B. ACO-RU connection and RRH-RU RoF channel model

The considered fronthaul exploits the high capacity of fiber links between the ACO and the RRHs and the high spectrum availability in the RRH-RU mmWave links. In particular, the ACO communicates with each RU via analog RoF transmissions of the properly encoded DL traffic. In the optical domain, we assume that at least one wavelength is available to each RRH and conveys the analog signals of all RUs served by the specific RRH and CBBU. Additional wavelengths can be assigned if necessary according to the WDM technique. In the wireless domain, for the RRH-RU communication, the 57-66 GHz band is used. The available spectrum can be split in half in order to be allocated separately to RUs with traffic belonging to two different directions, i.e., 4 GHz are available for UL traffic and 4 GHz for DL traffic (Fig. 2).

For the exchange of control signals between ACO and RUs, two out-of-band channels of 80 MHz bandwidth, one for DL and one for UL direction, are used. In DL direction, the RRH broadcasts the signals to the RUs it serves, whereas in UL direction, the code division multiple access scheme is employed, allowing the concurrent transmission of multiple RUs over the same channel according to a specific coding scheme that assigns a different code to each RU [22].

Regarding the RRH-RU channel, we assume that each RU k located in a distance x_k from an RRH m managed by DC n . The RU can use a number of b_k RoF channels out of a total number B of available channels, each offering bandwidth B_0 available for DL traffic. Thus, it can be served with a RoF data rate r_k equal to:

$$r_k^{\text{RoF}} = b_k B_0 \log_2(1 + SNR_k), k \in \mathcal{K}_{n,m}, n \in \mathcal{N}, m \in \mathcal{M} \quad (1)$$

where SNR_k is the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and $b_k \in [1, B], k \in \mathcal{K}$. Denoting as $p_{n,m}^{\text{Tx}}$ the transmission power of

RRH m , $\psi(x_k)$ the average path loss related to the RU k and as v_k the average noise power, the SNR of the RU is calculated as [23]:

$$SNR_k = p_{n,m}^{\text{Tx}} - \psi(x_k) - v_k. \quad (2)$$

For the estimation of SNR, it is assumed that the mmWave path loss is affected by both line-of-sight (LOS) and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) components that occur with probability $\pi^{\text{LOS}}(x_k)$ and $\pi^{\text{NLOS}}(x_k)$, respectively. Thus, it holds that $\psi(x_k)$ (dB) is equal to [24]:

$$\psi(x_k) = \pi^{\text{LOS}}(x_k)\zeta^{\text{LOS}}(x_k) + \pi^{\text{NLOS}}(x_k)\zeta^{\text{NLOS}}(x_k), \quad (3)$$

where $\pi^{\text{NLOS}}(x_k)$ can be calculated as:

$$\pi^{\text{NLOS}}(x_k) = (1 - \pi^{\text{LOS}}(x_k)), \quad (4)$$

and $\pi^{\text{LOS}}(x_k)$ is given by:

$$\pi^{\text{LOS}}(x_k) = 18/x_k(1 - e^{(-x_k/63)}) + e^{(-x_k/63)}. \quad (5)$$

The values ζ^{LOS} and ζ^{NLOS} reflect the path loss values in cases LOS and NLOS, respectively, and are estimated as follows [25]:

$$\zeta(x_k) = P_0 + 10\epsilon \log_{10}(x_k) + \gamma_k(\text{dB}) + \delta_k(\text{dB}), \quad (6)$$

where P_0 is the path loss at the reference distance x_0 and ϵ is the path loss exponent that indicates the rate at which the path loss increases with distance. The values γ_k and δ_k represent the shadowing and the small-scale fading, respectively.

C. Fronthaul packet delay and GoS

The packets generated by each CBBU are added to a queue and are transmitted via ETH link to the ACO, which forwards each packet to the corresponding RU via the RoF channels dedicated to the RU. Thus, throughout the path from CBBU m , in DC n , to RU k via the RRH m , the fronthaul delay $d_k(n, m, s_k, b_k)$ experienced by a packet with size l_k destined to RU k that uses the functional split s_k and occupies b_k RoF channels is estimated as:

$$d_k = d_{n,m}^{\text{Q}} + d_{n,m,\text{ACO}}^{\text{Prop}} + d_{k,n,m,\text{ACO}}^{\text{Tx}} + d_{\text{ACO},n,m}^{\text{Prop}} + d_{k,n,m}^{\text{Prop}} + d_{k,\text{ACO}}^{\text{Tx}}, \quad (7)$$

where $d_{n,m}^{\text{Q}}$ is the waiting time at the queue of CBBU m in DC n , $d_{n,m,\text{ACO}}^{\text{Prop}}$ and $d_{k,n,m,\text{ACO}}^{\text{Tx}}$ are the propagation and transmission delays, respectively, in a CBBU to ACO link that supports data rate $r_{n,m}^{\text{ETH}}$. The terms $d_{\text{ACO},n,m}^{\text{Prop}}$ and $d_{k,n,m}^{\text{Prop}}$ refer to the propagation delays in the optical medium (ACO to RRH) and the wireless medium (RRH m to RU k), respectively. The value $d_{k,\text{ACO}}^{\text{Tx}}$ is the transmission delay in the RoF channel between ACO and RU k that depends on the RoF data rate r_k^{RoF} achieved for k according to the experienced SNR and the allocated bandwidth.

In this context, the NM aims to assign the RUs to CBBUs and RRHs, allocate RoF channels to RUs and select functional splits between CBBUs and RUs in a way that the highest possible number of RUs experience fronthaul delay that respects the delay constraints imposed by the split type they use. Thus,

the following condition should hold for the highest possible number of RUs:

$$d_k(n, m, s_k, b_k) \leq D(s_k), n \in \mathcal{N}, m \in \mathcal{M}, \quad (8)$$

$$s_k \in \mathcal{S}, b_k \in [1, B], k \in \mathcal{K},$$

where $D(s_k)$ is the maximum acceptable delay for the functional split type $s_k \in \mathcal{S}$ used by k and b_k is the number of RoF channels allocated to k .

Letting $z_{n,m,k} \in \{0, 1\}$ be a variable that denotes whether RU k is associated with CBBU and RRH m in DC n , each RU k should be served by a specific CBBU and RRH, i.e., $\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} z_{n,m,k} = 1$, using at least one RoF channel, i.e., $b_k \geq 1$ and a functional split s_k with delay threshold $D(s_k)$. The higher layer split that can be used by an RU is $s_k = s^{\text{min}}$. We define a vector \mathbf{w} with size $|\mathcal{K}|$ such that each of its elements w_k denotes the occurrences of the required condition in Eq. (8). The element w_k is described as $w_k = \{d_k(n, m, s_k, b_k) - D(s_k), k \in \mathcal{K}\}^+$, where $\{\cdot\}^+$ denotes a projection on the set \mathbb{R}^+ that allows the representation of positive delay differences, i.e., $d_k(n, m, s_k, b_k) > D(s_k)$ as positive real numbers and the non-positive delay differences, i.e., $d_k(n, m, s_k, b_k) \leq D(s_k)$ as zero.

The ratio $g^{\text{FH}} \in [0, 1]$ of the number of RUs that do not meet their delay constraints over the total number of RUs $|\mathcal{K}|$, i.e., the fronthaul GoS, can be estimated as follows:

$$g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{b}) = \frac{\|\mathbf{w}\|_0}{|\mathcal{K}|}, \quad (9)$$

where $\mathbf{z} = \{z_{n,m,k} \in \{0, 1\}, \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, m \in \mathcal{M}, k \in \mathcal{K}\}$, $\mathbf{b} = (b_1, \dots, b_{|\mathcal{K}|})$ and $\|\mathbf{w}\|_0$ is the l_0 norm that denotes the number of non-zero elements of \mathbf{w} , i.e., the number of RUs that experience delay higher than the delay threshold imposed by the selected functional split type. The value g^{FH} has to be minimized in the considered optimization problem. The minimization of \mathcal{L}_0 -norm requires its approximation using a continuous function [26]. In our work, we use the following approximation [27]:

$$\|\mathbf{w}\|_0 \approx \sum_{k=1}^{|\mathcal{K}|} (1 - e^{-\nu|w_k|}), \quad (10)$$

where the two parts of the equation are strictly equal when the parameter ν approaches zero.

D. Power consumption model

We focus on the power consumption related to the operation of CBBUs and RRHs that can be switched on and off according to the fronthaul load related to the active RUs. The total fronthaul power consumption p^{FH} can be therefore estimated as the sum of p^{CBBUs} , which is the power consumption of active CBBUs and their DCs and p^{RRHs} , which is the power consumption of active RRHs and the corresponding RoF links between the ACO and the RRHs [28]. We thereupon describe the calculation of each of the two terms.

Letting $u_n \in \{0, 1\}$ be a variable that denotes whether DC n is off or on (i.e., when at least one CBBU m in DC n serves at least one RU, then $u_n = z_{n,m,k} = 1$ for at least

one $k \in \mathcal{K}$), $p_n^{\text{DC,act}}$ and $p_n^{\text{DC,idle}}$ the power consumed by DC n when it is active or idle, respectively, $z_{n,m,k} \in \{0, 1\}$ the variable that denotes whether RU k is associated with CBBU m and $\kappa_{n,m}\sigma_{n,m,k}^{\alpha_{n,m}}$ the power consumption of active CBBUs, p^{CBBUs} can be estimated as:

$$p^{\text{CBBUs}}(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{z}) = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} (u_n p_n^{\text{DC,act}} + (1 - u_n) p_n^{\text{DC,idle}}) + \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} z_{n,m,k} (\kappa_{n,m} \sigma_{n,m,k}^{\alpha_{n,m}}) \quad (11)$$

where the values $\kappa_{n,m} > 0$ and $\alpha_{n,m} > 1$ refer to the multiplication and exponent factors required for the polynomial approximation of $\kappa_{n,m}\sigma_{n,m,k}^{\alpha_{n,m}}$ value [29]. The Eq. (11) can be transformed to the following concise form:

$$p^{\text{CBBUs}}(\mathbf{z}) = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left(z_{n,m,k} \left(\frac{p_n^{\text{DC,act}}}{|\mathcal{M}_n| |\mathcal{K}_{n,m}|} + \kappa_{n,m} \sigma_{n,m,k}^{\alpha_{n,m}} \right) + (1 - z_{n,m,k}) \frac{p_n^{\text{DC,idle}}}{|\mathcal{M}| |\mathcal{K}| - |\mathcal{M}_n| |\mathcal{K}_{n,m}|} \right). \quad (12)$$

The value p^{RRHs} is the sum of the RoF link power consumption p^{link} that depends on the RoF data rate offered to RU k and the power consumption of the RRHs and is calculated as [30]:

$$p^{\text{RRHs}} = p^{\text{link}} + p^{\text{oper}}. \quad (13)$$

Denoting as $p_{n,m}^{\text{max}}$ the power dissipation of the ACO-RRH link related to RRH m in DC n and $C_{n,m}$ the capacity of the fiber link between ACO and RRH m managed by DC n , the value p^{link} is equal to:

$$p^{\text{link}}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{b}) = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} z_{n,m,k} \frac{\left(\frac{r_k^{\text{RoF}}}{C_{n,m}} p_{n,m}^{\text{max}} \right)}{|\mathcal{K}_{n,m}|}, \quad (14)$$

where r_k^{RoF} depends on the bandwidth b_k allocated to each RU k , considering Eq. (1). Letting $y_{n,m} \in \{0, 1\}$ the variable that denotes whether RRH m in DC n is off or on, the power consumption p^{oper} related to the operation of the RRHs, both active and idle is calculated as:

$$p^{\text{oper}}(\mathbf{y}) = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} (y_{n,m} p_{n,m}^{\text{act}} + (1 - y_{n,m}) p_{n,m}^{\text{idle}}) \quad (15)$$

where $p_{n,m}^{\text{act}}$ and $p_{n,m}^{\text{idle}}$ refer to the power consumed to keep RRH m in DC n active and idle, respectively. The Eq. (15) can be also written as follows:

$$p^{\text{oper}}(\mathbf{z}) = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left(z_{n,m,k} \frac{p_{n,m}^{\text{act}}}{|\mathcal{K}_{n,m}|} + (1 - z_{n,m,k}) \frac{p_{n,m}^{\text{idle}}}{|\mathcal{K}| - |\mathcal{K}_{n,m}|} \right). \quad (16)$$

Considering the aforementioned equations, the total fronthaul power consumption is equal to:

$$p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{b}) = p^{\text{CBBUs}}(\mathbf{z}) + p^{\text{RRHs}}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{b}), \quad (17)$$

assuming that the ACO and the RUs are always on, regardless of the load levels. As it can be observed, the decision regarding the association of an RU k with a CBBU m in DC n , i.e., the value of $z_{n,m,k}$ determines whether CBBU m in DC

n is activated, i.e., $y_{n,m} = 1$. Hence, the fronthaul power consumption can be expressed as a function of the variables \mathbf{z} and \mathbf{b} .

III. FRONTHAUL RESOURCE ALLOCATION PROBLEM FORMULATION

In the considered fronthaul architecture, the resource allocation problem involves i) the assignment of available CBBUs and RRHs to the RUs, ii) the sharing of the available bandwidth in the RoF channels between the RUs served by each RRH, and, iii) the selection of the functional split between each RU and CBBU. In this context, the aim of the NM is to jointly minimize the fronthaul grade-of-service and power consumption. These two objectives can be expressed as the total fronthaul performance loss Φ^{FH} , which should be minimized. To this end, taking into account Eq. (9) and Eq. (17), the considered problem can be formulated as:

$$\min_{\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{b}} \quad \Phi^{\text{FH}} = g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{b}) + p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{b}) \quad (18a)$$

$$\text{subject to} \quad \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} b_k \leq B, \quad (18b)$$

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_{n,m}} r_k^{\text{RoF}} \leq C_{n,m} \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, m \in \mathcal{M}, \quad (18c)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} z_{n,m,k} = 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (18d)$$

$$\sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} z_{n,m,k} \leq |\mathcal{K}|, \quad (18e)$$

$$z_{n,m,k} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall n \in \mathcal{N}, m \in \mathcal{M}, k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (18f)$$

$$s_k \in \{s^{\text{min}}, \dots, s^{\text{max}}\} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (18g)$$

$$b_k \in [1, B] \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad (18h)$$

The constraint (18b) refers to the sum of the allocated channels to $|\mathcal{K}|$ RUs, which should be less or equal to the number of available channels B , whereas the constraint (18c) states that the RoF data rates of the RUs in the set $\mathcal{K}_{n,m}$ served by RRH m , which is managed by DC n , should not exceed the capacity $C_{n,m}$ of the link between ACO and RRH m . The constraint (18d) imposes the association of each RU k with only one CBBU m in a DC n and the constraint (18e) ensures that (18d) holds for all RUs. The subsequent constraints set the acceptable values of the resource allocation parameters. More specifically, the constraint (18f) states that $z_{n,m,k}$ is a binary variable. Next, the constraint (18g) denotes the functional split options that are available for each RU and (18h) imposes that the number of channels b_k that can be allocated to each RU k should be in the range $[1, B]$.

The bi-objective non-convex optimization problem described by Eq. (18a) is solved by proper selection of the integer values of \mathbf{z} , \mathbf{s} and \mathbf{b} parameters. Pareto-optimal solutions can be derived by exhaustive search of the state space defined by the decision variables using the ε -constraint method [31]. This method optimizes one of the objectives using the other objectives as constraints, leading to a solution that is proven to be weakly Pareto optimal even when the optimization

problem is non-convex, as the one studied in our work. For the application of the ε -constraint method in our problem, we define as \mathbf{X} the matrix that combines the decision vectors $(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{b})$, which denote the association of RUs with CBBUs, RRHs and DCs (\mathbf{z}), the selected functional split types per RU (\mathbf{s}) and the allocation of RoF channels to each RU (\mathbf{b}). Denoting as $|\mathcal{K}|$ the number of RUs and $|\mathcal{M}|$ the number of available CBBUs and related RRHs, it holds that \mathbf{X} is a $|\mathcal{K}| \times (|\mathcal{N}||\mathcal{M}| + 2)$ matrix, where each element $x_{k,j}$, $k = 1, \dots, |\mathcal{K}|$, $j = 1, \dots, |\mathcal{N}||\mathcal{M}| + 2$ can obtain the following values:

$$x_{k,j} \in \begin{cases} \{0, 1\}, & j = 1, \dots, |\mathcal{M}||\mathcal{N}| \\ \mathcal{S} = \{s^{\min}, \dots, s^{\max}\}, & j = |\mathcal{N}||\mathcal{M}| + 1 \\ [1, B], & j = |\mathcal{N}||\mathcal{M}| + 2 \end{cases}$$

In the optimization process, we consider the row vector \mathbf{x} derived from matrix \mathbf{X} as the vector of decision variables. Next, we formulate the bi-objective problem as a single objective problem, where the fronthaul power consumption $p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x})$ is minimized using the fronthaul GoS $g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x})$ as constraint according to the ε -constraint method, considering also the constraints of the original problem:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (19a)$$

$$\text{subject to } g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}) \leq \varepsilon, \quad (19b)$$

$$\text{constraints (18b)-(18h)}, \quad (19c)$$

where ε denotes the constraint imposed to the objective function $g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x})$.

Definition 1. A solution \mathbf{x} is weakly Pareto optimal if there exists no other solution \mathbf{x}' , such that i) $g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}) < g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}')$ and ii) $p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}) < p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}')$.

According to (Definition 1), a solution is weakly Pareto optimal if there is no other solution that improves both objective functions simultaneously.

Proposition 1. The ε -constraint method results in a weakly Pareto optimal solution of the fronthaul power consumption minimization problem.

Proof. This proposition can be proved by contradiction. Let \mathbf{x}' be a solution of the ε -constraint problem that is not weakly Pareto optimal. This means that there exists a solution \mathbf{x}'' that satisfies the following conditions hold: i) $g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}'') < g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}')$ and ii) $p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}'') < p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}')$. Then, it also holds that $g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}'') < g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}') \leq \varepsilon$, which means that solution \mathbf{x}'' is feasible. However, it also holds that $p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}'') < p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}')$, which contradicts the assumption that \mathbf{x}' is a solution of the problem. Hence, the solution \mathbf{x}'' must be weakly Pareto optimal. \square

It is possible that there exists no solution that minimizes both objectives simultaneously. In order to observe the possible trade-offs between the two objectives, the derivation of Pareto front is required, which can be performed by iterative variation of value ε . In our work, we applied an exhaustive search (ES) based algorithm for the exact Pareto front calculation [32]. Each Pareto-front point corresponds to a dominant solution of the ε -constraint problem for a different ε -constraint value.

However, the computational complexity of this method is high and probably intractable even for a small number of RUs, CBBUs, functional split options and RoF channels. Moreover, it results in a set of solutions for each load level, i.e., number of RUs that need to be served and their 5G NR channel status. In this case, the NM should apply additional criteria to select a suitable solution. Hence, more practical heuristic methods should be used, such as SA, which can iteratively and stochastically explore the state space defined by the decision parameters $(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{b})$ and timely converge to a fronthaul resource allocation by deriving solutions close to Pareto front [21]. Our proposal, the DFRA algorithm, is based on SA and is described in the following Section IV.

IV. DYNAMIC FRONTHAUL RESOURCE ALLOCATION

In this section, we describe the operation of the SA based DFRA algorithm that dynamically allocates CBBUs, RRHs, bandwidth and functional splits to RUs in an SDN-enabled converged Fi-Wi fronthaul architecture. The aim of the optimization process is to jointly minimize the fronthaul GoS g^{FH} and power consumption p^{FH} , activating CBBUs and RRHs according to predicted fronthaul delay levels. The proposed algorithm consists of two phases, i.e., the initialization phase and the optimization phase, which are performed by NM with the aid of SDN framework. Moreover, DFRA estimates the fronthaul delay considering the model described in Section IV-C. The computational complexity of the DFRA algorithm is discussed in Section IV-D.

A. Weighted fronthaul resource allocation problem

For the derivation of solutions using the DFRA algorithm, before the execution of the SA process, the bi-objective problem should be converted to a single objective that contains normalized versions of the original functions. This adaptation is performed using the weighted sum (WS) method and a scheme that normalizes the objective functions by the actual intervals of their variation over the Pareto optimal set, giving the same magnitude to each objective function [33].

With the WS method, the problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{x}} \Phi_{\text{WS}}^{\text{FH}} = \omega_1 g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}) + \omega_2 p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}) \quad (20a)$$

$$\text{subject to constraints (18b)-(18h)}, \quad (20b)$$

where the weighting factors $\omega_1, \omega_2 \in [0, 1]$ and $\omega_1 + \omega_2 = 1$. These weights are given by $\omega_i = \phi_i \theta_i$, $i = 1, 2$ where ϕ_i are the weighting factors that reflect the relative importance of each objective. The values θ_i are the normalization factors that arrange the units and magnitude of the two objectives. They are estimated using the utopian points θ_i^U and nadir points θ_i^N of each function, which denote the lower and upper bounds of the Pareto optimal set, respectively, and are given by:

$$\theta_i = \frac{1}{\theta_i^N - \theta_i^U}, i = 1, 2. \quad (21)$$

Using these points, each objective function can be bounded, i.e., the following conditions hold:

$$0 \leq \frac{g^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}) - \theta_1^{\text{U}}}{\theta_1^{\text{N}} - \theta_1^{\text{U}}} \leq 1 \text{ and } 0 \leq \frac{p^{\text{FH}}(\mathbf{x}) - \theta_2^{\text{U}}}{\theta_2^{\text{N}} - \theta_2^{\text{U}}} \leq 1, \quad (22)$$

which allow us to obtain the same magnitude for each function.

B. Algorithm operation

As described in Section III, the formulated optimization problem can be solved using an exhaustive search approach that determines the optimal allocation of CBBUs, RRHs and channels to the RUs. However, this solution is computationally intensive even for small scale fronthaul architectures due to the high number of $(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{b})$ allocations that should be evaluated even for a few RUs. In order to avoid the evaluation of such a large search space, SA can be used as an effective heuristic alternative. So far, it has been applied to a wide range of high-dimensional network performance optimization problems (e.g., [34], [35], [36], etc.).

SA is a stochastic optimization approach that employs randomized perturbations of an initial solution in order to approximate the optimal value of a given objective function and is inspired by the SA process in metallurgy, where the melted metal is cooled in a slow manner in order to finally achieve a final form with fewer defects [37]. Particularly, the SA process begins using a high initial system temperature T^{init} which gradually decreases down to a final temperature T^{end} according to a cooling schedule that determines the convergence rate of the process and is regulated by the temperature descent parameter ξ .

In each iteration, a candidate solution is generated and is used for the evaluation of the objective function. If the new solution reduces the objective function, then it is accepted as the current solution. Otherwise, it is accepted according to a probability that depends on the current temperature. This conditional transition is known as the Metropolis criterion [38]. The initial temperature needs to be high enough in order to ensure that most of the generated candidate solutions meet the Metropolis criterion. This behavior enables SA to avoid local minima and continue searching for a globally optimal solution by occasionally moving towards solutions that yield higher objective values.

Exploiting the aforementioned characteristics of SA, the DFRA algorithm performs a similar process that consists of two phases, i.e., the initialization phase and the optimization phase, which are performed by the RA module of NM using the network status information provided by the TM module. In the initialization phase of Algorithm 1 (steps 1-5), the TM module updates the RU status, i.e., the load and the SNR levels, via the control channels of the RUs that enable the communication of RUs with one CBBU and RRH of a specific DC that is always active. In step 2, the RA module of NM initializes the parameters related to SA. In step 3, RA performs an initial random allocation of the RUs to the DCs, CBBUs and RRHs. Each RU uses the most centralized split option s^{max} and uses random number of RoF channels. Next, in steps 4-5, the initial temperature of the SA process is set and the fronthaul cost is estimated considering the initial allocation.

The optimization phase described in steps 6-30 performs the SA process, repeating a number of steps for a maximum number of iterations I in each temperature level, until the final temperature value is reached. At the beginning of the optimization phase (steps 8-14), a candidate solution is generated and evaluated. The RA module selects randomly an RU k , assigns it randomly to CBBU m in a DC n , randomly allocates to it b_k channels and selects a functional split s_k according to $\pi(s)$. The value $\pi(s)$, i.e., the ratio of the number $|\mathcal{K}_{n,m,s}|$ of RUs in CBBU m in DC n that use the selected split and the number $|\mathcal{K}_{n,m}|$ of RUs currently assigned to m and n , makes the probability π that a specific functional split is selected proportional to the number of RUs in the specific CBBUs and DC that use the same split.

For the fronthaul cost evaluation, in step 15, the CalcDelay function (Algorithm 2) described in Section IV-C is used by RA in order to estimate the fronthaul delay considering the candidate solution. Subsequently, the RA module checks whether further improvement of the fronthaul cost can be achieved using the generated solution according to the precision parameter ε . In steps 19-27, the candidate solution $(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{b}_i)$ is evaluated according to the Metropolis criterion, i.e., it is accepted as the current solution if it yields lower fronthaul cost, otherwise it is accepted according to the probability $e^{(\Phi_i^{\text{FH}} - \Phi^{\text{FH}})/T}$. If the candidate solution is accepted, then it is selected as the current solution. The SA process ends in steps 29-30, where the temperature is decreased by a factor $\xi > 0$, according to a geometric cooling schedule [39].

The DFRA algorithm terminates with steps 31-32, applying the derived solution $(\mathbf{z}_{\text{best}}, \mathbf{s}_{\text{best}}, \mathbf{b}_{\text{best}})$. At this point, the RA module can de-activate fronthaul components that are not utilized. If no RUs are associated with a CBBU, it is considered to be idle. In case that all CBBUs in a DC do not serve any RUs, it is considered to be in idle mode. Finally, the resources determined by DFRA are allocated to the fronthaul components and RA notifies the fronthaul components about the new configuration.

C. Delay estimation in DFRA algorithm

As discussed in Section IV-B, in each iteration i of the SA process performed by the DFRA algorithm, a new candidate solution is generated and the resulting fronthaul cost is evaluated. For this evaluation, the CalcDelay function (Algorithm 2) is used, which performs the estimation of the fronthaul delay experienced by each RU according to Eq. (7), considering the candidate solution, i.e., the current assignment of CBBUs and RRHs (\mathbf{z}_i) , functional splits (\mathbf{s}_i) and RoF channels (\mathbf{b}_i) to RUs.

Using the CalcDelay function, the RA module of NM first estimates the transmission delay in the optical medium considering a packet size l_k for each RU k and in the wireless medium with an allocated bandwidth b_k . Next, we explain the calculation of the term $d_{n,m}^{\text{Q}}$ that refers to the waiting time of packets at the queue of CBBU m in DC n we consider an M/D/1/N queue with finite capacity in a system having a single CBBU, where packet arrivals are determined by a Poisson process and service times are fixed for the time period

Algorithm 1 Dynamic fronthaul resource allocation algorithm

Input: Set of DCs \mathcal{N} , available CBBUs and RRHs \mathcal{M} , RUs \mathcal{K} , functional splits \mathcal{S} , RoF channels \mathcal{B} , delay thresholds per split type $D(s_k)$, data rates $r_{n,m}^{\text{ETH}}$, capacity levels $C_{n,m}$ and packet sizes l_k .

Output: Resource allocation $(\mathbf{z}, \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{b})$ that minimizes Φ^{FH} .

Initialization phase:

- 1: The TM module of NM updates the RU status, i.e., load λ_k and SNR_k values $\forall k \in \mathcal{K}$.
- 2: The RA module of NM sets values for initial temperature T^{init} , final temperature T^{end} , temperature descent rate ξ , number of iterations I and precision parameter ε .
- 3: All DCs, CBBUs and RRHs are initially active, the RUs are randomly allocated to them and use random number of RoF channels and the functional split s^{max} .
- 4: $T \leftarrow T^{\text{init}}$
- 5: Initial fronthaul cost Φ_0^{FH} is estimated as the result of the initial allocation $(\mathbf{z}_0, \mathbf{s}_0, \mathbf{b}_0)$ according to Eq. (18a).

Optimization phase:

- 6: **while** $T > T^{\text{end}}$ **do**
 - 7: **for** $i = 1 : I$ **do**
 - 8: RA selects randomly an RU k , assigns it to random CBBU m and DC n with random b_k and functional split s_k according to value $\pi(s) \leftarrow \frac{|\mathcal{K}_{n,m,s}|}{|\mathcal{K}_{n,m}|} \forall s \in \mathcal{S}$.
 - 9: Select randomly a probability $\pi(s)$ and a random number $\pi \in [0, 1]$.
 - 10: **if** $\pi > \pi(s)$ **then**
 - 11: Select split s for RU k assigned to the specific CBBU m in DC n .
 - 12: **else**
 - 13: Keep previous functional split for RU k .
 - 14: **end if**
 - 15: Update solution $(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{b}_i)$ and calculate fronthaul cost Φ_i^{FH} , estimating the delays with CalcDelay $(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{b}_i)$.
 - 16: **if** $\frac{|\Phi_i^{\text{FH}} - \Phi_{i-1}^{\text{FH}}|}{\Phi_{i-1}^{\text{FH}}} < \varepsilon$ **then**
 - 17: break;
 - 18: **end if**
 - 19: **if** $\Phi_i^{\text{FH}} - \Phi_{i-1}^{\text{FH}} \leq 0$ **then**
 - 20: Set $\Phi_i^{\text{FH}} \leftarrow \Phi_{i-1}^{\text{FH}}$ and update $(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{b}_i)$.
 - 21: **else**
 - 22: **if** $\pi \in [0, 1] > e^{(\Phi_i^{\text{FH}} - \Phi_{i-1}^{\text{FH}})/T}$ **then**
 - 23: Set $\Phi_i^{\text{FH}} \leftarrow \Phi_{i-1}^{\text{FH}}$ and update $(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{b}_i)$.
 - 24: **else**
 - 25: Set $\Phi_i^{\text{FH}} \leftarrow \Phi_{i-1}^{\text{FH}}$ and keep previous solution $(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{b}_i) \leftarrow (\mathbf{z}_{i-1}, \mathbf{s}_{i-1}, \mathbf{b}_{i-1})$.
 - 26: **end if**
 - 27: **end if**
 - 28: **end for**
 - 29: $T \leftarrow \xi \cdot T$
 - 30: **end while**
 - 31: According to solution $(\mathbf{z}_{\text{best}}, \mathbf{s}_{\text{best}}, \mathbf{b}_{\text{best}})$, RA makes idle DCs, CBBUs and RRHs not associated with any RU.
 - 32: **Return** $\Phi_{\text{best}}^{\text{FH}}$ and assignment of DCs, CBBUs, RRHs, RoF channels and functional splits to RUs $(\mathbf{z}_{\text{best}}, \mathbf{s}_{\text{best}}, \mathbf{b}_{\text{best}})$.
-

between two consecutive executions of DFRA algorithm in a realistic network. More specifically, it is assumed that the packets of RUs in set $\mathcal{K}_{n,m}$ are added to the M/D/1/N queue of the CBBU with length $q_{n,m}$ according to a Poisson process with packet arrival rate $\lambda_{n,m} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_{n,m}} \lambda_k$. The value λ_k depends on the used functional split type and the load of RU k , as discussed in Section II-A2. It has been proved that in the case of M/D/1/N queue the waiting time $d_{n,m}^{\text{Q}}$ can be derived using the following closed form expression [40]:

$$d_{n,m}^{\text{Q}} = \left(q_{n,m} - 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{q_{n,m}-1} \beta_i - q_{n,m}}{\rho_{n,m} \beta_{q_{n,m}-1}} \right) \tau_{n,m}, \quad (23)$$

where $\rho_{n,m} = \lambda_{n,m} \tau_{n,m}$ is the utilization factor. The term $\tau_{n,m}$ denotes the average service time in the queue of CBBU m in DC n , i.e., the time required for a packet with mean packet size $\mathbb{E}[l_{n,m}]$ to be transmitted over the CBBU-ACO link with supported ETH data rate $r_{n,m}^{\text{ETH}}$ and propagation delay in the optical medium $d_{n,m,\text{ACO}}^{\text{Prop}}$. The value $\tau_{n,m}$ can be calculated as:

$$\tau_{n,m} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[l_{n,m}]}{r_{n,m}^{\text{ETH}}} + d_{n,m,\text{ACO}}^{\text{Prop}}. \quad (24)$$

The coefficients β_i required for the estimation of the waiting time in Eq. (23) are given by the following closed form expression [40]:

$$\beta_i = \sum_{j=0}^i \frac{(-1)^j}{j!} (i-j)^j e^{-(i-j)\rho_i} \rho_i^j, \forall i \geq 1, \quad (25)$$

setting $\rho_i = \rho_{n,m} \forall i = 1, \dots, q_{n,m}$ and $\beta_0 = 1$.

Algorithm 2 CalcDelay function for delay prediction

Input: Current allocation of DCs, CBBUs, RRHs, functional splits and RoF channels to RUs given by current solution $(\mathbf{z}_i, \mathbf{s}_i, \mathbf{b}_i)$ in iteration i .

Output: Predicted delay $d_k(n, m, s_k, b_k)$ for each RU k .

- 1: **for** $k = 1 : |\mathcal{K}|$ **do**
 - 2: **if** $\rho_{n,m} > 1$ for CBBU m in DC n used by RU k **then**
 - 3: Set $d_k \leftarrow \text{MAX}, k \in \mathcal{K}_{n,m}$.
 - 4: **end if**
 - 5: Calculate packet transmission delays $d_{k,n,m,\text{ACO}}^{\text{Tx}}$ and $d_{k,\text{ACO}}^{\text{Tx}}$ in optical and wireless medium for packet size l_k , ETH data rate $r_{n,m}^{\text{ETH}}$ and bandwidth b_k for RU k .
 - 6: Calculate d_k according to Eq. (7) and Eq. (23) with current $\mathcal{K}_{n,m}$ and λ_k related to the currently selected functional split s_k .
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: **Return** Predicted delay values $d_k \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$.
-

D. Computational complexity of DFRA algorithm

The computational complexity of the DFRA algorithm (Algorithm 1) is related to its optimization phase that performs the SA process. In each iteration, the NM generates a candidate solution in order to evaluate the expected fronthaul cost. Considering an initial temperature T^{init} , a final temperature

T^{end} and a temperature descent parameter ξ , the total number of fronthaul cost evaluations I^{DFRA} can be calculated as:

$$I^{\text{DFRA}} = \left\lceil \frac{T^{\text{init}} - T^{\text{end}}}{\xi} \right\rceil I, \xi \in (0, 1), \quad (26)$$

where I is the maximum number of iterations in each temperature level. Moreover, for each fronthaul cost evaluation, the CalcDelay function (Algorithm 2) needs to evaluate the expected fronthaul delay for each RU. Therefore, the resulting computational complexity of the DFRA algorithm is $O(I^{\text{DFRA}}|\mathcal{K}|)$.

It should be also noted that the convergence rate of the DFRA algorithm is regulated by the parameter ξ that is related to the SA process. On one hand, a fast reduction of the temperature would make SA miss the optimal solution. On the other hand, a too slow reduction may result in very slow convergence. Hence, the value of ξ should be selected considering the trade-off between the optimality of the derived solution and the resulting convergence time.

The operation of SA implies that after a fixed number of iterations, which can be selected considering the computational complexity, the best solution is accepted as an approximation to the optimal solution. In contrast, a heuristic approach based on exhaustive search of the possible solutions would be impractical. More specifically, an exhaustive evaluation of the fronthaul cost that is induced by all the possible combinations of resources would induce much higher computational complexity.

Assuming $|\mathcal{M}|$ available CBBUs and RRHs, $|\mathcal{S}|$ functional split types and B RoF channels, an RU k can use a combination of resources selected out of $|\mathcal{M}||\mathcal{S}|B$ of possible allocations. Thus, for $|\mathcal{K}|$ RUs, the total number I^{ES} of fronthaul cost evaluations that would be required can be estimated as:

$$I^{\text{ES}} = \frac{(|\mathcal{K}| + |\mathcal{M}||\mathcal{S}|B - 1)!}{|\mathcal{K}|!(|\mathcal{M}||\mathcal{S}|B - 1)!}, \quad (27)$$

which yields a computational complexity $O(\log(I^{\text{ES}}))$.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we assess the performance of the proposed algorithm in DL traffic scenarios considering varied number of RUs and varied bandwidth levels in the RU 5G NR channels. We compare DFRA with i) a baseline scheme that assigns the active RUs to CBBUs in a round robin (RR) manner that uses the Option 7 functional split with a fixed RoF channel allocation and does not take into account the fronthaul power consumption, and ii) an exhaustive search (ES) based heuristic scheme. We use the Monte Carlo method for our simulations and consider a 95% confidence interval for the presentation of our simulation results.

We use the network settings described in Section V-A in order to evaluate the DFRA algorithm in terms of GoS, average delay, power consumption, energy efficiency and centralization degree. In Section V-B, we describe the calculation of the fronthaul data rates per functional split type used in our simulations. The simulation results are discussed in Section V-C. Considering the power consumption model described

in Section II-D, the fronthaul energy efficiency ee (bits/Joule) is calculated as:

$$ee = \frac{r^{\text{FH}}}{p^{\text{FH}}}, \quad (28)$$

where r^{FH} is the fronthaul throughput given by:

$$r^{\text{FH}} = \frac{\mathbb{E}[l_k]}{\mathbb{E}[d_k(n, m, s_k, b_k)]}, \quad (29)$$

and p^{FH} is the fronthaul power consumption. The centralization degree (CD) is defined as the inverse of the computational cost of the different functional splits in CBBUs c^{CBBUs} and RUs c^{RUs} [41]:

$$\text{CD} = \frac{1}{(c^{\text{CBBUs}} + c^{\text{RUs}})}. \quad (30)$$

Assuming three functional splits, a set of three RAN functions $\mathcal{F} = \{f_0, f_1, f_2\}$ are defined, where f_0 is the low layer network function (RF, signal and analog processing, etc.) which is always placed in the RRH and f_2 is the high layer network function (i.e., PDCP). Letting c_k^1 and c_k^2 be the computational cost (CPU operations per b/s) of functions f_1 and f_2 located at RU k , respectively, and f_k^1 and f_k^2 , two variables that are equal to 1 when both f_1 and f_2 are performed at the RU and equal to 0 otherwise, the term c^{CBBUs} is calculated as:

$$c^{\text{CBBUs}} = \sum_{n \in \mathcal{N}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_n} \eta_{n,m} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_{n,m}} T_k(c_k^1(1-f_k^1) + c_k^2(1-f_k^2)), \quad (31)$$

where $\eta_{n,m}$ is the average cost (monetary units per cycle) for serving the RUs related to CBBU m in DC n and T_k the fronthaul throughput for k estimated as $T_k = l_k/d_k(n, m, s_k, b_k)$, $\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}_{n,m}}$ for selected split s_k and allocated RoF channel bandwidth b_k . In a similar manner, the term c^{RUs} can be estimated as:

$$c^{\text{RUs}} = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \eta_k T_k(c_k^1 f_k^1 + c_k^2 f_k^2), \quad (32)$$

where η_k the average cost related to RU k , assuming that $\eta_k > \eta_{n,m}$ with n and m being the DC and CBBU that serve k , respectively.

A. Simulation setup

We consider the Fi-Wi fronthaul of Fig. 1 with $|\mathcal{N}| = 2$ DCs each supporting up to 2 CBBUs and the related RRHs, i.e., $|\mathcal{M}| = 4$, and varied number $|\mathcal{K}|$ of RUs that serve users with DL traffic. More specifically, a number of $|\mathcal{K}| = \{4, 8, 12, 16\}$ RUs are used and each RU k can support 5G NR channels with bandwidth $b_k^{\text{RU}} = \{10, 20, 40\}$ MHz $\forall k \in \mathcal{K}$. Three functional split types between the CBBUs and the RUs are used ($|\mathcal{S}| = 3$), i.e., the Option 7 Intra-PHY split (s^{max}), the Option 6 and the Option 2 (s^{min}). The rest of the simulation parameters are summarized in Table II.

We have evaluated the performance of DFRA algorithm using the normalized single objective function of Eq. (20a). In the presented simulation results, we assume that the GoS and the power consumption are of equal importance and we set the weights $\phi_1 = \phi_2 = 0.5$. The utopian and nadir points of g^{FH} and p^{FH} are different for each load level. For $g^{\text{FH}}, \theta_1^{\text{U}} \in [0, 0.2]$

TABLE II: Simulation parameters

Parameter	Value
B	20
B_0	200 MHz
x_k	50-80 m
$d_{n,m,\text{ACO}}^{\text{Prop}}, d_{\text{ACO},n,m}^{\text{Prop}}$	1 us/200 m, fiber 4 km
$d_{k,n,m}^{\text{Prop}}$	0.2 us
$r_{n,m}^{\text{ETH}}$	10 Gb/s
$D(s_k)$ per split [42]	100 us (Opt.7), 250 us (Opt.6), 1.5 ms (Opt.2)
l_k	1500 B
ETH headers	22 B (max size 1522 B)
$\eta_{n,m}$	1
η_k	0.017
RoF channel model	(LOS, NLOS)
$p_{n,m}^{\text{Tx}}$	0.1 W
P_0	(63.4, 65.3)
ϵ	(1.72, 1.94)
γ_k	(1.18, 1.15), (4.48, 0.27)
δ_k	Rician ($s^{\text{R}} = 0.93$, $\sigma^{\text{R}} = 0.31, \kappa^{\text{R}} = 3$), Nakagami-m ($m^{\text{N}} = 4.68$, $\Omega^{\text{N}} = 1.03$)
Power consumption model	
$p_n^{\text{DC,act}}$	50 W [28]
$p_n^{\text{DC,idle}}$	5 W
$\kappa_{n,m}$	10^{-26}
$\sigma_{n,m,k}^{\alpha_{n,m}}$	$\frac{8}{1900} (13.5 \cdot 10^8 \text{cycles/s})^3$ [43]
$p_{n,m}^{\text{max}}$	2 W
$p_{n,m}^{\text{act}}$	17.8 W
$p_{n,m}^{\text{idle}}$	1.78 W
SA parameters	
T^{init}	100
T^{end}	1
ξ	0.95
I	2-5
ε	0.0001

and $\theta_1^{\text{N}} \in [0.1, 0.4]$, whereas for $p^{\text{FH}}, \theta_2^{\text{U}} \in [80, 200]$ and $\theta_2^{\text{N}} \in [100, 250]$.

B. Fronthaul data rates per functional split type

The fronthaul data rates are calculated in a different way for each functional split type, depending on the amount of information that needs to be exchanged between the CBBU and the RU. We will next describe the fronthaul data rate estimation performed for each split type in the downlink scenario according to the calculations mentioned in various 3GPP specification documents ([7], [44], [45], [46], [47]), along with the adaptations required by our simulation setup.

When the Option 7 (Intra-PHY) functional split is applied to an RU k , the functions of PHY layer are divided between the RU and the CBBU. 3GPP has defined three types of Intra-PHY splits, i.e., option 7.1, 7.2 and 7.3, that differ in the way physical (PHY) layer functions are separated between CBBUs and RUs [7]. In our study, we consider the option 7.2 split

where some of the PHY layer functions related to downlink traffic, i.e., iFFT, cyclic prefix addition, resource mapping and precoding functions, are performed by the RU, whereas the rest of PHY functions are managed by the CBBU. With this split type, the RU receives radio signal as a frequency domain IQ symbol instead of the time domain IQ sample, which increases the fronthaul load (in contrast to Option 8 (PHY-RF) split). The resulting fronthaul data rate $r_k^{\text{FH-Opt.7}}$ depends on the number of subcarriers N_k^{sc} used in the downlink channel, the symbol duration T_k^{s} , the bit resolution N_k^{q} used to quantize the signal samples, the number of receiving antennas N_k^{ant} and the fraction of RBs ρ_k^{RB} that are used and is estimated as:

$$r_k^{\text{FH-Opt.7}} = \frac{2N_k^{\text{sc}} \rho_k^{\text{RB}} N_k^{\text{q}}}{T_k^{\text{s}}}. \quad (33)$$

Given the subcarrier spacing Δf_k and the 5G NR channel bandwidth per RU b_k^{RU} , the number of used subcarriers is $N_k^{\text{sc}} = 0.9b_k^{\text{RU}}/\Delta f_k$. In our simulations, we assume that all of the available RBs of each RU are utilized, i.e., $\rho_k^{\text{RB}} = 1 \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$. We also set $T_k^{\text{s}} = 66.7$ us, $N_k^{\text{q}} = 15$, $N_k^{\text{ant}} = 2$ in a 2x2 MIMO setup, $\Delta f_k = 15$ KHz. Thus, for $b_k^{\text{RU}} = \{10, 20, 40\}$ MHz, we set $r_k^{\text{FH-Opt.7}} = \{0.54, 1.08, 2.16\}$ Gb/s, respectively.

With the Option 6 (MAC-PHY) functional split, all PHY layer processing is handled locally by RUs, whereas the MAC scheduling and the rest of higher layer functionalities are performed at CBBUs. Thus, the payload that has to be transmitted over the fronthaul includes the transport blocks and the scheduling control overhead. The fronthaul data rate $r_k^{\text{FH-Opt.6}}$ required by the use of Option 6 split depends on the peak data rate in the downlink 5G NR channel r_k^{DL} of each RU k and the rate of schedule/control signaling information of downlink channel $r_k^{\text{DL,ctrl}}$ and is calculated as:

$$r_k^{\text{FH-Opt.6}} = (r_k^{\text{DL}} + r_k^{\text{DL,ctrl}}) \rho_k^{\text{BW}} \rho_k^{\text{layer}} \rho_k^{\text{qam}} \quad (34)$$

where $\rho_k^{\text{BW}} = b_k^{\text{RU}}/b^{\text{LTE BW}}$ is the system bandwidth scaling ratio, with LTE reference bandwidth $b^{\text{LTE BW}} = 20$ MHz, $\rho_k^{\text{layer}} = N_k^{\text{layer}}/N^{\text{LTE layer}}$ is the MIMO layer scaling ratio, with $N^{\text{LTE layer}} = 2$, and $\rho_k^{\text{qam}} = 8/6$ is the QAM scaling ratio [47]. In our simulations, we set $r_k^{\text{DL,ctrl}} = 5$ Mb/s, $N_k^{\text{layer}} = 2$ and $\rho_k^{\text{layer}} = 1$, whereas ρ_k^{BW} is varied in accordance with the b_k^{RU} values. For $b_k^{\text{RU}} = \{10, 20, 40\}$ MHz, $r_k^{\text{FH-Opt.6}} = \{155, 309, 1246\}$ Mb/s, respectively.

When the Option 2 (PDCP/RLC) functional split is used, only the PDCP and RRC functions of the LTE protocol stack are centralized while the other functions are performed locally by the RU, which receives PDCP data units from the CBBU. In this case, the fronthaul data rate $r_k^{\text{FH-Opt.2}}$ is estimated in a similar logic as in the case of Option 6:

$$r_k^{\text{FH-Opt.2}} = r_k^{\text{DL}} \rho_k^{\text{BW}} \rho_k^{\text{layer}} \rho_k^{\text{qam}} + r_k^{\text{DL,ctrl}}, \quad (35)$$

with $r_k^{\text{DL,ctrl}} = 16$ Mb/s, whereas the rest of the parameters are adjusted similarly as in the fronthaul data rate calculation for Option 6. We set $r_k^{\text{FH-Opt.2}} = \{164, 318, 1248\}$ Mb/s, $b_k^{\text{RU}} = \{10, 20, 40\}$ MHz, respectively.

We should also note that the downlink data rate values r_k^{DL} used in the fronthaul data rate estimation for Options 2 and 6 are an approximation of the maximum supported data rate in

the downlink 5G NR channel of each RU, calculated as described in [45]. This data rate depends on several parameters, such as number of aggregated component carriers, number of supported layers, modulation order, number of RBs, type of 5G NR numerology and frequency range that are used. More specifically, assuming a number J_k of aggregated component carriers j of RU k , maximum number of supported layers v_k^j per carrier, maximum supported modulation order Q_k^j , the maximum coding rate $R^{\max} = 948/1024$, maximum RB allocation L_k^j for 5G NR channel bandwidth per RU b_k^{RU} , average orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM) symbol duration in a subframe T_k^s (in s) (for 5G NR numerology $\mu = 0$ that supports subcarrier spacing equal to 15 kHz) and the overhead for downlink channel in FR 1 $o^{\text{DL}} = 0.14$, the maximum supported data rate r_k^{DL} of RU k (in Mb/s) is estimated as:

$$r_k^{\text{DL}} = 10^{-6} \sum_{j=1}^{J_k} v_k^j Q_k^j R^{\max} \frac{12L_k^j}{T_k^s (1 - o^{\text{DL}})}. \quad (36)$$

In our simulations, we set that $J_k = 1$, $v_k^j = 2$, and $Q_k^j = 8 \forall k \in K$, whereas the RB allocation L_k^j varies per simulation scenario. In particular, for channel bandwidth $b_k^{\text{RU}} = \{10, 20, 40\}$ MHz and full RB usage, the RBs that are occupied at each RU k are $L_k^j = \{52, 106, 216\}$, respectively. Therefore, the corresponding estimated downlink data rates are $r_k^{\text{DL}} = \{111, 227, 462\}$ Mb/s, respectively.

C. Simulation results

We next evaluate the DFRA, ES and RR schemes considering different load levels, as induced by different numbers of active RUs and varied 5G NR bandwidth levels in the RUs.

In Fig. 3, the average fronthaul delay achieved by the DFRA, the ES and the RR scheme is shown. The allocation of functional split types for varied number of RUs when DFRA is applied is illustrated in Fig. 4. We first observe that DFRA provides a good approximation of the delay values achieved by the ES scheme for all load levels. A similar observation can be made for the resulting power consumption (Fig. 6).

Additionally, with DFRA, the delay is much lower than the delay threshold imposed by the selected functional split and results in $g^{\text{FH}} = 0$ in all cases. Notably, for $b_k^{\text{RU}} = 20$ MHz and $b_k^{\text{RU}} = 40$ MHz, the reduction in the fronthaul delay reaches 45% and 53%, respectively. This result can be attributed to the main operational characteristics of DFRA that configure the fronthaul resources in accordance with the load levels, i.e., the dynamic selection of functional split types, the activation of CBBUs and RRHs and the allocation of RoF channel bandwidth.

In contrast, when the RR scheme is used, in case of $b_k^{\text{RU}} > 10$ MHz and $|\mathcal{K}| > 8$, the delay is higher than the 100 us threshold of the Option 7 split and $g^{\text{FH}} > 0$ due to the use of fixed RoF channel bandwidth that does not adapt to the increased load. It should be also noted that DFRA is able to meet the fronthaul delay constraints using the minimum possible number of CBBUs and RRHs, as depicted in Fig. 5. In particular, for $b_k^{\text{RU}} < 40$ MHz, either one ($|\mathcal{K}| < 12$) or two CBBUs are active ($|\mathcal{K}| \geq 12$), whereas with RR scheme,

Fig. 3: Delay vs number of active RUs

Fig. 4: Functional splits for different RU bandwidth

all DCs, CBBUs and RRHs are active regardless of the load levels.

The effect of power consumption consideration applied by the DFRA scheme is illustrated in Fig. 6. It can be seen that due to the use of fewer CBBUs and corresponding RRHs and activation of fewer links, DFRA outperforms the RR scheme in terms of fronthaul power consumption. It achieves a reduction

Fig. 5: Active CBBUs and RRHs vs number of active RUs

Fig. 6: Power consumption vs number of active RUs

of 55% and 43% for $|\mathcal{K}| = 4$ and $|\mathcal{K}| = 16$, respectively, when $b_k^{\text{RU}} > 10$ MHz is used. We can also observe that for all tested 5G NR channel bandwidths, the use of RR induces similar power consumption levels, as all CBBUs and RRHs are concurrently in use.

At this point, let us now jointly inspect the resulting power consumption depicted in Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 that shows the Pareto front for different number of active RUs in case that $b_k^{\text{RU}} = 20$ MHz $\forall k \in \mathcal{K}$. The DFRA algorithm results in solutions with GoS practically equal to zero (lower than 0.05 in the Pareto front), whereas the power consumption is in the range $[80, 110]$. This means that the DFRA algorithm converges to the solution with the lowest achievable GoS. The power consumption value is higher than the minimum possible, however, it is still close to the Pareto front. It is important to note that other solutions from the Pareto front could be selected. Moreover, the WS method enables the modification of the weighting factors in a way that more importance is given to the power consumption. Although this change could guide the SA process to a more energy-efficient solution, a GoS value higher than zero, i.e., the violation of the delay constraints of some RUs, may not be a desirable result.

The benefits of applying DFRA are also displayed in the energy efficiency performance. As demonstrated in Fig. 8, the energy efficiency achieved by DFRA is significantly higher than the energy efficiency achieved by RR scheme, achieving an increase from 73% to 246%. This effect occurs due to both the use of fewer fronthaul resources by DFRA and the selection of less centralized split types that lead to lower experienced delay and higher fronthaul throughput for almost all $|\mathcal{K}|$ values. For $|\mathcal{K}| \geq 12$ and $b_k^{\text{RU}} = 40$ MHz, the energy efficiency of DFRA exhibits a downward trend, which can be justified by the lower fronthaul load and resulting throughput induced by the use of less centralized split types and the concurrent activation of an additional DC, along with more CBBUs and RRHs.

The dynamic adaptation of the functional split types used by DFRA affects also the levels of the CD metric that is estimated as the inverse of the total computational cost. In Fig. 9 the normalized CD values in all load cases for the two schemes are depicted. The inherent flexibility of DFRA allows the use of

Fig. 7: Pareto front for different number of active RUs ($b_k^{\text{RU}} = 20$ MHz)

Fig. 8: Energy efficiency vs number of active RUs

less centralized splits when higher number of RUs are active, as demonstrated by the CD levels that are lower than those achieved by the RR scheme for most fronthaul load levels. Even though the RR scheme yields lower computational cost, as it keeps most functions centralized, this result occurs at the expense of power consumption and, in some cases, the experienced delay. For instance, when $|\mathcal{K}| > 8$ and $b_k^{\text{RU}} = 40$ MHz, the resulting delay is higher than the delay threshold of Option 7 split. Moreover, the energy efficiency is lower than the energy efficiency achieved by DFRA algorithm and the resulting g^{FH} is higher than 0.

In a nutshell, the performance assessment of DFRA algorithm proves that the flexibility it offers in the selection of the functional split type used between CBBUs and RUs and the CBBUs and RRHs that should be activated is able to improve the fronthaul resource allocation in an SDN-enabled analog RoF fronthaul. DFRA can adapt the functional split type to the fronthaul load levels and jointly allocate CBBUs and RoF channel bandwidth to the RUs respecting the delay thresholds

Fig. 9: Centralization degree vs number of active RUs

imposed by each split type and reducing the fronthaul power consumption as much as possible.

We have also observed that the computational cost is a factor that may affect the decision regarding the functional splits used by the RUs and the assignment of RUs to CBBUs and DCs. Therefore, the minimization of computational cost could be also included in the resource allocation optimization performed by DFRA along with the other two performance metrics. As a future research line, various fronthaul performance indicators could be jointly optimized using multi-objective SA for the derivation of trade-off solutions.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a dynamic fronthaul resource allocation (DFRA) algorithm designed for analog RoF Fi-Wi fronthaul has been presented and evaluated via simulations. The proposed algorithm leverages the SDN capabilities and uses an SA based heuristic process in order to jointly minimize the fronthaul GoS and power consumption by assigning CBBUs and RoF channel bandwidth to RUs and selecting the functional split used between each RU and its corresponding CBBU. The performance assessment has demonstrated that DFRA outperforms the baseline round-robin scheme in terms of GoS and power consumption for all fronthaul load levels. The increase of the number of active RUs and the used 5G NR channel bandwidth and the use of more centralized functional splits require the activation of more CBBUs. However, DFRA achieves GoS equal to zero in all cases, selecting the proper CBBU, RoF channel bandwidth and functional split type for each RU in a way that the fronthaul power consumption is also minimized, achieving performance close to the optimal.

As novel fronthaul designs are introduced with the aim of meeting the 5G NR capacity demands, our work can provide useful insights for the development of resource management techniques adapted to Fi-Wi fronthaul with virtualization and dynamic functional splitting capabilities. Our approach can serve as an intuitive paradigm that stochastic optimization techniques like SA, can be exploited in SDN-based networks for deriving approximate solutions to problems induced by complex fronthaul architectures.

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